

wypadku przez zespół ratownictwa medycznego, są mniej narażeni na niebezpieczeństwa czyhające na miejscu zdarzenia, otrzymują również o wiele wyższe wynagrodzenie i mogą się czuć bardziej spełnieni zawodowo. W badaniach Cipora i in. (2014) najwyższe wskaźniki wypalenia pielęgniarki otrzymały właśnie w wymiarze obniżona satysfakcja zawodowa.

Kierunek dalszych badań

W dalszych badaniach można zwrócić uwagę na dodatkowe zmienne psychologiczne, jak: zadowolenie z życia zawodowego oraz poczucie satysfakcji z życia oraz zdolność do empatii. Empatia zalicza się do podstawowych umiejętności związanych z komunikacją w medycynie. Lekarze i pielęgniarki empatyczni mogą lepiej zrozumieć pacjenta i są w stanie lepiej wejść w relację wspierającą. Empatia jest podłożem prawidłowej relacji terapeutycznej oraz efektywnego leczenia.

Empatia oraz jej korelacje ze składowymi wypalenia zawodowego: wyczerpanie emocjonalne, depersonalizacja oraz obniżenie satysfakcji z wykonywanej pracy mogą stanowić cenną inspirację dla zgłębienia problematyki wypalenia zawodowego wśród medyków.

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DOCTORAL STUDENTS AT RISK ACADEMIC AND PROFESSIONAL SUPPORT: QUALITY MANAGEMENT ISSUES

Keywords: doctoral education, doctoral candidates at risk, cultural landscape, quality culture, quality management.

For decades, the cultural landscape of education in Ukraine was determined by the colonization ambitions of the Russian Federation and efforts to bring the Ukrainian state back into the orbit of its influence. The totalitarian and bloody twentieth century, like the imperial-tsarist system of Moscovia before it, took away entire generations of talented Ukrainian scientists, artists, and public figures - the Ukrainian creative elite, the blossom of our nation of that periods. The Bolshevik regime destroyed, suppressed, persecuted, shot, starved... It was made that Ukrainian identity had no place in Ukraine [Snyder]. "Shot Revival", a phenomenon that, unfortunately, remains unjustifiably little researched and reinterpreted by contemporaries, is one of the most terrible pages of the history of the 20th

century, associated with the destruction of Ukrainian talents due to national identity [Zabuzhko]. That was the purposeful colonization of everything Ukrainian, including education and science [Luciuk].

During the years of independence, attempts to decolonize the higher education system were rather formal. Only after the Revolution of Dignity (2014), with the coming of democratic forces to power, concrete steps were taken to cleanse socially important spheres from the influence of the "fifth column", which had been shaking the state from the inside for decades.

It was these phenomena that determined the political, cultural, and academic background, within which in 2022 the war found the most vulnerable category related to doctoral education - graduate students. Since one tragic night in February 2022, Ukrainian doctoral students (doctoral candidates) along with their mentors acquired a new status – Ukrainian scholars at risk.

In the wake of the full-scale unprovoked war aggression in Europe in 2022, the educational landscape has been significantly altered, necessitating adjustments in many plans. Despite these challenges, it remains vital for the Ukrainian higher education sector to maintain its resilience and continue its development.

The situation is dramatically changing because some higher education and research institutions have been damaged or destroyed, and these numbers continue to grow. Facilitated by their experience during the COVID-19 crisis, most Ukrainian universities continue to offer teaching to doctoral students through blended formats regarding wartime restrictions. However, it must be admitted that Russian strikes on electricity infrastructure have made research all but impossible. Added to the challenges caused by the COVID-19 pandemic (the loss of everyday contacts at the campus, the lack of social interaction, difficulties in accessing laboratories or other research facilities; organizing online training, theses defense, and supervision; the lack of networking opportunities and doctoral schools underfunding, struggling doctoral candidates' rates increasing), the war has caused new challenges connected with appropriately addressing the needs of such a diverse category of PhD students as doctoral candidates at risk. This includes those who have fled or are at risk of fleeing Ukraine due to the war, those who have remained in the country, including displaced PhD students within Ukraine, doctoral students in refugee-like situations, and Ukrainian doctoral candidates who are refugees abroad. Special attention is required for struggling doctoral candidates and international doctoral students connected to Ukrainian academia.

Totalitarian regimes like the one in the Russian Federation prioritize power and authority over the well-being of their citizens. As a result, the conflict is not just political, but also a fight for the freedom to choose one's own cultural identity. This provides a significant context for the advancement of *a new type of academic culture* in doctoral education within Ukraine - a *culture of university social responsibility* that prioritizes human values and addresses the real needs of Ukrainian researchers while providing early-career researcher-friendly support, both academic and professional. This is particularly crucial given the risks they face, including the threat of a "brain drain" as more scholars emigrate or become refugees. The aim is to prevent the loss of a new generation of scholars due to these challenges.

This encompasses addressing research capacity in wartime and post-conflict conditions, ensuring quality supervision and training, and institutional responsibility for supporting early-stage researchers, their societal engagement, mental health, well-being, and career track. These elements constitute a comprehensive system for developing

doctoral education and Quality Assurance, in line with the EUA Innovation Agenda 2026, EURODOC, and EUA-CDE initiatives and developments.

To successfully integrate the advanced European research values into Ukrainian doctoral programmes to achieve sustainability among scholars at risk at Ukrainian regional HEIs, many challenges need to be addressed:

- the public is prejudiced against advanced European research values and is unaware of its benefits;
- unsatisfactory research funding based on the leftover principle;
- continuing dependence on Russian-language research journals without quality peer-review procedures;
- lack of meeting academic integrity requirements as a crucial limiting factor for scientific development;
- there is a lack of understanding what are the necessary steps for integrating advanced European research values into Ukrainian doctoral programmes.

Social support and academic engagement are key elements of doctoral education quality studies (Altbach, 2011; Nerad; Bogle; Kohl; O’Carrol, Peters, Scholz, 2022). Societal dimensions of the problem include doctoral well-being; research capacity and self-efficacy (Kokotsaki, 2023); PhD imposter syndrome; doctoral student attrition; research supervision (Guerin & Green, 2015).; professional identity development; isolation feelings in doctoral programs (Lovitts, 2001; Ali & Kohun, 2007; Szadkowski, 2017, 2029).

Academic engagement and support of vulnerable categories of learners is a crucial thematic issue within the EU and globally. The proposed research is framed by the Council of Europe/UNESCO Lisbon Recognition Convention (2017); the Paris Ministerial Communiqué (2018); and the Rome Ministerial Communiqué (2020). Since 2022, under the Council of the European Union wide-ranging policies and measures have been put in place to support Ukrainian refugee students, including doctoral candidates, in higher education in Europe (European Commission, EACEA, Eurydice, EURODOC reports).

Such a human-centered, democratic, and empathetically enriched strategy for developing the cultural landscape of doctoral education in Ukraine gives a chance to decolonize spheres of education, science, and research at the national level. Undoubtedly, strengthening scientific and intellectual potential should become an integral part of Ukraine's recovery plan.

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ПРОФЕСІЙНИЙ РОЗВИТОК ПЕДАГОГІЧНИХ ПРАЦІВНИКІВ: ПРОГРАМИ БЕЗПЕРЕРВНОГО ПРОФЕСІЙНОГО РОЗВИТКУ ТА ПІДВИЩЕННЯ КВАЛІФІКАЦІЇ ПЕДАГОГІВ

Ключові слова: професійний розвиток, безперервний професійний розвиток, підвищення кваліфікації, педагогічні працівники, освітній процес, інноваційні технології, цифрові навички, методи викладання, онлайн-курси, електронне навчання, гейміфікація в освіті, педагогічні компетенції, інтерактивні методи навчання.

Професійний розвиток педагогічних працівників є основою для забезпечення високої якості освіти. Педагогічна діяльність вимагає постійного оновлення знань, навичок і компетенцій, оскільки сучасні умови освіти швидко змінюються. Одним із ключових аспектів професійного розвитку є безперервне підвищення кваліфікації педагогів. Програми безперервного професійного розвитку дають можливість педагогам не лише оновлювати свої знання, але й удосконалювати професійні навички, адаптуватися до змінюваних вимог освітнього середовища. Це важливий елемент для створення інноваційного освітнього процесу, який відповідає сучасним потребам суспільства.

Програми безперервного професійного розвитку педагогів є важливим інструментом у системі освіти, що забезпечує їх адаптацію до нових вимог та стандартів. Вони включають в себе курси, тренінги, вебінари, семінари, майстер-класи, які дозволяють педагогам вдосконалювати свої знання і навички протягом усієї кар'єри. Безперервний професійний розвиток сприяє не тільки теоретичному зростанню, але й практичному вдосконаленню педагогічних умінь.

В Україні, як і в інших країнах, безперервний професійний розвиток педагогів став однією з важливих складових освітньої реформи. Зокрема, в Україні були розроблені програми для підвищення кваліфікації викладачів, які забезпечують відповідність вимогам нових освітніх стандартів, змісту навчальних програм та технологій навчання. Програми безперервного професійного розвитку зосереджуються на таких напрямках, як впровадження інноваційних педагогічних технологій, розвиток цифрових навичок, формування нових підходів до оцінювання